

INFORAC/UNEP-MAP

Agreement between Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA) and National Research Council (CNR) - Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (IREA)

Analysis, design and development of packages

Report R1

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1 Summary

This Report (R1) concerns the work carried out first in the needs analysis and then in the design of the different packages, which in the case of Dashboard and GeoStories led to the identification of already mature software solutions and the sketching out of an initial development, while in the case of the Knowledge Hub (KHub) it stopped at the creation of a preliminary mock-up, since the requirements gathered showed that a dedicated development would be needed.

2 Introduction

This deliverable is in the framework of the agreement between Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA) and Consiglio Nazionale per le Ricerche (CNR) - Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (IREA) (No. 0003070/2022). In this agreement the Parties undertake to jointly develop study and research activities aimed at defining a strategy for the management and dissemination of knowledge in the Mediterranean area, with reference to a feasibility study, design and definition of methodologies and technologies related to the development of the UNEP-MAP Knowledge Platform (KP) through innovative tools based on the different and complementary competences of INFO/RAC and CNR-IREA.

After the data sources identification during the phase 0 of the project and the definition of possible users for the platform, the instruments of Geostories and Dashboards were identified as powerful dissemination tools with different purposes:

- Raising awareness on UNEP-MAP topics and work among Mediterranean citizens (Ocean Literacy actions).
- Governance instruments for private and institutional stakeholders and MAP components to create effective reports, guidelines and scenarizations on MAP topics.
- Instruments useful for research purposes, effective to parse MAP data, especially in preliminary data analysis phases (Exploratory Data Analysis).

Once defined the possible usage of the instruments, a Google form was created to involve UNEP-MAP Regional Activity Centers (which often represent data providers in the workflows depicted during Phase 0) in the definition of dashboards' and geostories' themes that would be of any interest for the designed public.

The questionnaire (<https://forms.gle/GgbFerVXoLL6iBwEA>) asks to imagine a case study and the related material (documents or layers) to be involved in the creation of the product (Dashboard or GeoStories), choosing the material from a dropdown menu reporting all the identified data sources but giving also the possibility to define additional material with respect to the ones discovered during Phase 0. Advice on the styling (appearance, colors, types of graphs) of the tool is also welcomed.

The questionnaire has been dispatched starting from April 2023, some suggestions about possible themes to be proposed both in GeoStories and Dashboards have been received, but there isn't still a consistent number of responses to be analyzed. The survey will be forwarded again through the Centers and suggestions will be passed both to ISPRA and the implementing partner to create the identified tools using the identified material.

About the Knowledge Hub a different procedure was followed, in fact, there are no existing software solutions that can be used for the functionalities designed and deemed necessary against the requirements gathered. Chapter 5 summarises the ideational process to arrive at a mockup proposal for the knowledge hub as well.

3 Proposed solution for Dashboard

Examining data sources and focusing on data types, their accessibility, and the possibilities to analyze them, some technological solutions for dashboards have been tested, giving precedence to open-source software.

In particular Mapstore¹, Apache Superset², Grafana³, Tableau⁴, Microsoft Power BI⁵ products have been examined and some features and characteristics have been evaluated in each solution:

- Intuitiveness of User Interface: due to the large variety of users potentially involved in dashboards usage the intuitiveness of the user interface is evaluated. It should be friendly and capable to suggest at best optimum solutions for the scope.
- Easiness of update and maintenance: updates operations and maintenance should be as easy as possible to build an instrument capable to overpass the duration of the contract with the implementing partner (together with this aspect also appropriate training activities on tools must be considered).
- Possibility to insert additional tools with respect to the default ones: the possibility to extend the dashboard with the most appropriate instrument after the type of data and the scope of the dashboard is fundamental.
- Possibility to download data aggregated through the dashboard to select a subset of the dataset/s involved and perform further eventual analyses (also offline or out of the dashboard itself).
- Possibility to export as image or PDF the widgets to fix and use them “as they are” in other products such as publications, reports, guidelines, and eventually the possibility to integrate them in websites using HTML language.
- The fact that the tool is Open Source or not.

All these aspects have been evaluated for each one of the examined tools with a score from 1 to 5 where 1 stays for “poor”, 2 stays for “fair”, 3 stays for “good”, 4 stays for “very good”, and 5 stays for “excellent”. The Open Sourceness of the tool is represented by a boolean field, instead.

	Intuitiveness of UI	Easiness of update and maintenance	Possibility to add tools (out than default)	Possibility to download aggregated data	Possibility to export widgets (graphs/tables/maps/etc.)	Open Source	Total Score

¹ <https://geosolutionsgroup.com/technologies/mapstore/>

² <https://superset.apache.org>

³ <https://grafana.com>

⁴ <https://www.tableau.com>

⁵ <https://powerbi.microsoft.com>

Mapstore	4	5	5	5	5	Y	24
Apache Superset	5	5	5	5	5	Y	25
Grafana	4	3	3	5	4	Y	19
Tableau	4	4	4	5	4	N	21
Power BI	4	3	4	5	4	N	20

Table 1 - Evaluation of different tools, with scores and total.

In particular, from the testing of different solutions two tools were selected: Mapstore and Apache Superset.

The first one is already integrated into GeoNode (which is the software used for the Data Hub of the upcoming Knowledge Management Platform) and allows a consistent personalization of the interface and the set-up of a certain number of tools and widgets. Apache superset is also performant and allows, among other things, a wider variety of graphs and functionalities with respect to Mapstore and it is fully compatible with the already existing system. Both the solutions allow the integration of third party (also non open source) software granting the wider flexibility of usage than the possible.

The suggested choice is then Mapstore, since it is already integrated into GeoNode and it doesn't require to add further dependencies to the existing system, granting stability. If, in the near or far future, more functionalities will be necessary to represent UNEP-MAP data, the integration of Apache Superset should be considered to achieve better dissemination and analysis results.

Further interesting application that could be integrated into the KMP system could be a virtual private or public space allowing advanced and statistical analyses on data by means of R Shiny package (exploiting R language) or Jupyter Lab (exploiting Python language). However, these functionalities are not foreseen to be implemented in the prototype, but they could be effectively interesting when implementing the Knowledge Exchange part of the platform. In fact, together with a Project Management Tool, a deeper analysis instrument functioning as virtual lab could surely be of some interest for the stakeholders and UNEP-MAP components.

Using the suggested tool (Mapstore) a first live mockup has been implemented exploiting some data about Accidents in the Mediterranean Sea from MEDGISMAR project in InfoMAPNode and already available for testing. Some screenshots of the appearance of the dashboard and functionalities are reported in Figure 1, 2 and 3. As highlighted, by connecting widgets It is possible to filter data on a map or a specific interval on a temporal scale or a specific section of a graph. It is also possible to

download both data and images representing the widgets, as like as the integration of the entire dashboard or a single widget inside a webpage.

Figure 1 - Comprehensive overview of the test dashboard.

Figure 2 - Possibility to download filtered data from the single widget (left); possibility to connect widget to another widget (example: when the map is zoomed only displayed features are considered in the barplot, right).

Share with people and groups

This Page

<https://infomapnode.info-rac.org/catalogue/#/dashboard/1176>

Embed This Dashboard

<https://infomapnode.info-rac.org/apps/1176/embed>

Figure 3 - Possibility to embed the dashboard into a website.

4 Proposed solution for GeoStories

Technological solutions for Geostories with specific interesting features such as media and webpage integration or download of the story are generally more limited than for Dashboards. In fact, two main solutions are available to create these powerful dissemination instruments: Storymaps (by ESRI) and Geostories (by GeoNode). Other evaluated solutions are Data Stories from Terria.io, Geotales or the MapBox GL JS PLUGIN but they all require specific plugins or pieces of code to be integrated into the main platform to function properly (e.g. Leaflet for Terria.io).

In the following table features of both Geostories and Storymaps are compared focusing on the main functionalities that a Geostory should include for the purposes of the KMP:

- The possibility to incorporate maps and text.
- The possibility to add media such as images, videos or audio files.
- The possibility to incorporate webpages and the possibility to navigate them through the story.
- The possibility to create a geocarousel that links text to places and shows them in sequence.
- The possibility to add resources both from online public repository and ad hoc private spaces inside the hosting platform.
- The possibility to download the story in different file formats (such as PDF and PNGs).

	Incorporate maps and text	Add media	Add webpages (responsive)	Create a geocarousel (map responsive with text)	Add online and stored resources	Download the story	Open source
Geostories	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Storymaps	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N

Table 2 - Comparison between the functionalities of Storymaps (by ESRI) and Geostories (by GeoNode).

Following the same criteria already used for the dashboards, both Storymaps and Geostories have been tested trying to reproduce the same “story”. Both instruments gave proof of good flexibility and capacity to integrate various tools. Widget types and their styling are equivalent. Both instruments are highly customizable and give the user the possibility to insert media coming from public repositories or from private storage.

Storymaps are a bit more fluid with respect to Geostories in transitions while integrating text and maps in carousel mode, but the product is not Open Source and it is always possible, eventually, to integrate a Storymap in a Geostory, while it is not possible the other way around. Since the instruments are nearly equivalent in performance, it is advisable to use Geostories first and eventually integrate Storymaps only if Geostories reveal their limits in representing UNEP-MAP necessities. In this way stability of the platform is granted by not adding external pieces of code to the system.

Screenshots of appearance and functionalities of a mockup Geostory built in InfoMAPNode is shown in Figure 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Figure 4 - Appearance of a sample Geostory in GeoNode.

Figure 5 - Embedding of a responsive website.

Figure 6 - Embedding of media (video) from Youtube.

Figure 7 - Dynamic geocarousel (text connected to specific locations).

5 Preliminary mock-up proposal for Knowledge Hub

On the basis of the use case citizens described in the previous section a first mock-up of the graphic user interface was designed and sketched.

5.1 Starting proposal mock-up

The KHub default access page was thought for the citizens role in order to ease their understanding of the main contents of the KHub. It relies on the categorization of the contents into Themes, i.e., topics, and their relationships represented by a knowledge graph where nodes are the topics (containing sets of documents maps etc.) and the edges are the relationships, i.e., contain the documents that belong to both the topics represented by the nodes connected by the edge. Indeed by clicking on a node allows visualizing the list of its items, i.e., documents, maos etc.; by clicking on an edge allows to visualize the intersection of the items of the connected nodes.

Figure 8 - Thema filter representation of KHub preliminary mock-up.

The menu on the first row of the GUI allows to filter the KHub contents based on different criteria:

- Geofilter allows to perform selection of georeferenced contents like maps of geotagged documents by asking range or punctual queries, by specifying toponymies or by drawing on the map the area or point of interest for the contents to be retrieved. The result is the list of documents and maps that are georeferenced in the area of interest;
- keyword filter allows to specify keyword based selections on the indexes of both textual documents, multimedia documents and metadata of maps;
- the list of retrieved items will be shown in decreasing order of satisfaction to the query;
- the Time filter allows to specify a time range for the selection of contents released in that specific time period;
- source filter allows to select only specific resources of interest and then filters items that satisfy other filters only if they are provided by these resources;
- finally Thema filter allows to select items belonging to a topic by clicking on the nodes of the knowledge graph.

The following mockup is the screenshot sketch when all filters are activated together: the user has specified that she/he wants to retrieve documents about “libellule” (see the keyword) released after 2004 (see the time bar selection) geolocated in China (see the range query bounding box) , that the items must be provided by the specified resource (a submenu of “source filter” allows to select the resources of

interest) and that are about a specific Theme (a submenu of Thema filter allows to select the theme of interest).

Figure 9 - Geofilter section of KHub with geographic representation of all data that fit with time, keywords, sources, and thematic filters.

The necessary features for the realisation of the KHub are specified in the slides at this address: https://isprambiente-my.sharepoint.com/:p:/g/personal/annalisa_minelli_isprambiente_it/EbG6rrwvo1RNgQTgLNenV1IB7Nw6nLhLqBDSJVhXyLNLzg?e=aP1G2o

6 Conclusions

What emerged in this phase (Phase 1) of the project is a direct consequence of all the information gathered in Phase 0: list of the sources and list of related data, but also the description of the roles and workflows related to users such as administrator, Decision Maker/Stakeholder, Citizen and RAC/researcher.

The identification of specific roles, but above all the creation and study of workflows, accompanied and followed by more technical evaluations (table 1 and 2), made it possible to identify possible software solutions to build an initial proposal concerning the Dashboard (figures 1 and 2) and GeoStories (figures 4, 5, 6 and 7). On the other hand, the process of creating an initial mock-up for the KHub was different, for which contents based on different criteria were designed for the time being and only a few drawings sketching out the functionality of the user interface were proposed (Figures 9 and 10). A final proposal will be the subject of the final phase of the project (Phase 2).